

Preliminary Report on the Effects of Shoulder Motion Restriction on Motion Sickness Under Lateral Acceleration Conditions in Darkness

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Abstract

In this study, we investigated the effects of shoulder movement restriction on motion sickness under lateral acceleration conditions. Participants seated in a car seat in darkness were subjected to repetitive lateral movements, and we compared the head movements and motion sickness progression with and without the movement restriction. The results showed that body movement restriction reduced trunk and resultant head movements significantly, as well as a significant reduction in motion sickness.

1. Introduction

Motion sickness, particularly car sickness among passengers, significantly diminishes comfort during travel. Addressing this issue has become increasingly important, especially with advancements in IT devices and the diversification of in-vehicle activities.

Among the theories explaining the mechanism of motion sickness, the sensory conflict theory, also known as the neural mismatch theory, posits that motion sickness arises when sensory information received from the sensory organs contradicts the expected patterns processed by the central nervous system (CNS) (Reason, 1978).

Regardless of the mechanism, substantial knowledge has also been accumulated from the perspective of body motion. For example, The Motion Sickness Dose Value (MSDV), as defined by the ISO 2631-1 standard, quantifies the likelihood of motion sickness by integrating frequency-weighted vertical acceleration over time, with greater values indicating a higher risk of motion sickness. Its foundation originates from the work of (McCauley et al., 1976), which established the relationship between vertical acceleration and motion sickness incidence. This metric is widely accepted; however, it is limited to handling vertical motion, among other limitations, which has prompted ongoing revisions to the ISO standard (Bos et al., 2022, 2024). Furthermore, it is known that

body motion influences motion sickness under more complex head movements. For instance, active tilting of the body to align the head with gravito-inertial acceleration (GIA)—the sum of gravitational and inertial accelerations—has been shown to reduce motion sickness during longitudinal sinusoidal acceleration (Golding et al., 2003) and slalom driving (Wada et al., 2012; Wada & Yoshida, 2016). From a vehicle design perspective, much effort has long been made, including suspension (Kajino et al., 2008; Papaioannou et al., 2021), as well as seat designs (Kato et al., 2021). In particular, a headrest with occipital bone support was developed and shown to reduce motion sickness (Kato et al., 2021).

The present research, hypothesized that restriction of shoulders by adding parts to a passenger seat reduces head motions without directly limiting head motion, leading to reduced motion sickness. Therefore, this study investigated the effects of shoulder movement restriction on motion sickness under lateral acceleration conditions. Participants seated in a car seat in darkness were subjected to repetitive lateral movements, and we compared the head movements and motion sickness progression with and without the movement restriction.

2. Method

2.1 Design

For this study, 14 participants were exposed to a lateral acceleration stimulus while seated in a car seat mounted on a linear motion platform (Fig.1). The only experimental factor was the body-fixed method, which had two levels: the presence or absence of a special movement restriction part designed to restrict lateral body movements. This factor was treated as a within-subject factor. Each participant experienced both body-fixed methods on two separate days, with at least one day in between sessions. The order of the conditions was counterbalanced. Both sessions for each participant were scheduled at approximately the same time of day. This study was approved by the Ethics Review Committee of the Nara Institute of Science and Technology.

2.2 Participants

Fourteen individuals (11 males and 3 females) with a mean age of 24.9 years ($SD = 3.4$) provided written informed consent to participate in the experiments. Participants were informed that the experiments could potentially induce motion sickness. They were also explicitly told that they could terminate their participation at any time and for any reason. Participants were compensated approximately \$40 for their participation. Prior to the experiments, motion sickness susceptibility of each participant was assessed using the Motion Sickness Susceptibility Questionnaire (MSSQ)(Golding, 2006). The mean percentile score was 40.3% ($SD = 28.9$), indicating a wide distribution of susceptibility to motion sickness.

2.3 Apparatus

In this study, a linear motion platform, as shown in Fig. 1, was used to apply lateral accelerations to the participants. Each participant was seated on a chair mounted perpendicular to the direction of motion. The backrest angle of the seat was set to approximately 19 degrees, and the headrest was removed to facilitate measurements. In the present research, a special part designed to restrict lateral body movements was installed on the seat.

The seat was positioned inside a cabin enclosed by black walls, ensuring the absence of visual cues for the participants. The internal dimensions of the cabin were approximately 0.85 m in width, 1.90 m in length, and 1.75 m in height. Even when participants tilted their heads or upper body, they did not come into contact with the cabin walls.

A motion capture system (VICON) with four cameras was used to measure the movements of the participant's head and upper body. The cameras were installed inside the cabin in such a way that they were not visible to the participants. Eight markers were affixed to each participant: four on the head (top, forehead, and two sides) and four on the upper body (two on the sternum and two on the acromion).

Fig.1: A linear motion platform used in experiments

2.4 Motion profile

The motion of the platform alternated between sinusoidal motion, in which the acceleration reached a maximum of 2 m/s^2 at a frequency of 0.3 Hz, and stops. As shown in Fig.2, six cycles of this motion were combined to form one set, lasting approximately one minute. A maximum of 16 sets were performed, resulting in a total measurement time of about 16 minutes if all sets were completed.

A 5-second interval was included between each set. During these intervals, which occurred once every minute, participants were asked to report symptom level of motion sickness using the MIsery Scale (MISC)(Bos et al., 2005).

Fig. 2: Motion profile for one of a total of 16 sets. Each set consists of six cycles of reciprocating motion with intermittent stops.

2.5 Procedure

As previously mentioned, the experiment was conducted over two days. On each day, the following procedure was carried out:

Each day began with an explanation of the experimental procedure. Participants were also asked about their physical condition on the day of participation to confirm that they were in good health. Motion sickness susceptibility of each participant was assessed using MSSQ only for the first day.

Then, each participant was seated in the seat on the motion platform in a normal sitting position and secured with a safety belt before being exposed to the acceleration applied by the platform. Participants underwent a maximum of 16 measurement sets under a single experimental condition. During each interval between two sets of motion, which occurred approximately every minute, participants were asked to report their MISC. The experiment was immediately terminated, and the motion platform stopped under either of the following conditions: 1) The participant's MISC reached or exceeded 6 for the first time, 2) The participant requested to stop the experiment for any reason. It is worth noting that there were no dropouts due to the second reason in the present study. After the motion challenges, participants' MISC was monitored at one-minute intervals.

2.6 Evaluation method

2.6.1 Motion sickness

The progression of motion sickness symptoms was evaluated using MISC (Bos et al., 2005), which is an 11-point subjective rating scale for symptom progression.

The total sum of all MISC values recorded over the 16-minute duration was used as a representative value for each individual and condition. For participants who dropped out before completing the session, their last observed MISC value was carried forward for the remaining duration to calculate the total.

2.6.2 Magnitude of Passenger's Body Movement

The movements of participants' head and upper body were measured using a motion capture system (VICON). For this study, the magnitude of head movement was represented by the average displacement of markers attached to the head, while upper body movement was represented by the average displacement of markers attached to the torso. For each participant, the magnitudes of head and trunk movements were determined as the relative displacements from their initial positions in each measurement set, and their root mean square (RMS) values were calculated.

2.6.3. Statistical analysis

When both normality and homoscedasticity were confirmed using the Shapiro-Wilk test and F-test, a paired t-test was performed. Otherwise, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for statistical analysis.

3. Results

3.1 RMS of the head and body lateral movement

The RMS values of the head and trunk movements are shown in Fig.3. Wilcoxon signed-rank tests revealed that the RMS values with the restriction were significantly smaller than those without the restriction ($p=0.000$ for head motion and $p=0.000$ for trunk motion).

Fig.3: RMS of head and upper body movements.

3.2 Motion sickness

The time history of MISC for each participant is shown in Fig.4. Fig.5 illustrates the total sum of the MISC for each body restriction condition. A paired t-test revealed that the MISC sum with the movement restriction was significantly smaller than that without restriction ($p=0.041$).

Fig.4: Time history of MISC progression for each participant

Fig.5 Sum of MISC

4. Discussion and conclusion

The results above demonstrated that body movement restriction successfully reduced trunk and resultant head movements significantly, thereby leading to a significant reduction in motion sickness. These findings suggest that restricting body movement could serve as an effective countermeasure for mitigating motion sickness under lateral acceleration conditions in the absence of visual cues.

The concept of suppressing head motion through seat design is commonly applied in seat development. Recently, a novel headrest designed to restrict occipital motion has been developed, demonstrating that it effectively reduces head motion and mitigates motion sickness (Kato et al., 2021). The key contribution of the present study is the finding that significant reductions in head motion and motion sickness can be achieved solely by restricting shoulder movement, without directly fixing the head. This approach offers the advantage of mitigating motion sickness while avoiding direct restraints on the head. Additionally, as demonstrated by (Golding et al., 2003; Wada et al., 2012, 2024; Wada & Yoshida, 2016), certain tilting motions of the head may reduce motion sickness more effectively than directly fixing it. The proposed method of restricting shoulder movement without directly fixing the head has the potential to be combined with such strategies, which could further enhance its effectiveness.

It is worth noting that (Kato et al., 2021) investigated the effectiveness of their method under visual task conditions, suggesting that the approach proposed in this study may yield similar benefits in such scenarios. Experimentally verifying these possibilities remains an important direction for future research.

In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the potential of shoulder movement restriction as an effective countermeasure for mitigating motion sickness under lateral acceleration conditions. By reducing head motion without direct head fixation, this approach addresses the limitations of

traditional head restraint methods and paves the way for innovative solutions that balance comfort and effectiveness in motion sickness mitigation.

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